

Deliverable
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.13
Workpackage 5

Responsible Partner: 2-AGES, 23-UoS

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Description of the task

Since the aim of work package 5 was to identify effects of environmental conditions that influence bacterial transformation, in task 5.3 a soil microcosm setting was created by utilizing non-manured agricultural soil. This task started only in August 2022 due to the lack of laboratory staff. After initial tests, we concluded that *A. baylyi* was the more suitable species to show the effects on soil microcosms. First, RNA isolation from soil microcosms was established and later on RT-TaqMan qPCR systems for two competence genes and several *A. baylyi* housekeeping/reference genes were designed. Pilot experiments were carried out with having a look at differential competence gene expression levels in relation to environmental stimuli (temperature shift, exposure to antibiotics, different nutrient levels). The first results of this task are shown below.

Description of the deliverable

The deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.13 (*Results of the soil microcosm experiments regarding environmental effects on competence gene expression*) is associated with task 5.3 (Effect of different environmental conditions on the expression of competence genes in *A. baylyi* determined using soil microcosms (M44-M56)).

Heat exposure was chosen as the environmental parameter, thus, soil samples were incubated at 35°C and at 20°C. The soil samples were spiked with the naturally transformable bacterium *Acinetobacter baylyi* in order to track the expression of some of its competence genes. RNA was isolated utilizing the RNeasy PowerSoil Total RNA Kit and spectrophotometrically quantified via the Nanodrop 2000/2000c. The RNA was isolated from the soil samples prior to incubation and spiking with *A. baylyi* (tinitial), immediately after spiking (tspike), six hours and 24 hours after spiking.

The obtained RNA was diluted to 10 ng/μL, followed by a RT-qPCR on the LC480 II to measure the expression of the 16S rRNA, functioning as the reference gene, and two transformation/competence-specific targets: *dprA* and *comA*. The delta delta Ct method was utilized for relative quantification.

Results

A 30 (*comA*)- to 40 (*dprA*)-fold decrease in target gene expression was noticeable in the *A. baylyi* spiked soils up to 6 hours at 35°C in comparison to the samples left at 20°C. However, this decrease vanished after 24h and the expression-levels of the 35°C and 20°C soil samples converged.

Figure 1: Temperature-dependent expression of competence-specific genes *dprA* and *comA* in relation to *16S rRNA* using the Delta Delta Ct method.

Next steps

This experiment will be repeated under improved conditions and an additional timepoint (3 hours after heat incubation) will be added to obtain more information about competence gene expression levels.

Conclusion

Preliminary results show that within a time window of 6 hours, expression of *A. baylyi* specific competence genes can be repressed due to heat exposure. This effect is time restrained as the mRNA-levels of *dprA* and *comA* are similar after 24h at either temperature. This observation indicates that uptake of free extracellular DNA by naturally competent soil bacteria might be reduced at elevated environmental temperatures.